

Comparison of aboveground arthropod diversity within pitch pine
and scrub oak barrens habitats on Nantucket Island with
emphasis on the beetle fauna

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Introduction

The implications of current land use and management practices on insect diversity is an important issue in conservation ecology because insects are so plentiful and can significantly impact net primary production and nutrient flow within a habitat (Carson and Root 1999, Tscharntke and Greiler 1995). In addition, insects interact with many species and management practices that alter these interactions may have profound affects on local diversity and ecological functioning within the habitat. The affects of habitat management practices on insect diversity within grasslands have mainly been studied within the context of the North American Central Plains. These studies typically investigated the affects of spring burns, ox or cattle grazing, or mowing management (Fay 2003). To date, Dunwiddie (1991) has provided the only investigation on the affects of burning and mowing management to aboveground arthropod communities in Nantucket's sandplain grasslands. In this study, the impact of fire and mowing disturbance on the abundance of aboveground arthropods was inconsistent between groups. Arachnida abundance was low after a spring burn, but Orthoptera (grasshoppers) were generally higher after the fire than in the reference plot (Dunwiddie 1991). After burning or mowing in August, the majority of insect Orders decreased except for the Homoptera. These results are similar to many others studies within grasslands that observed little consistency in response over major taxonomic groupings (Fay 2003).

The mosaic of habitats that comprise the pitch pine/scrub oak barrens on Nantucket Island have been under active management for many years with the primary motivation to preserve rare plant diversity. Pitch pine/scrub oak barrens extend from Maine south to New Jersey and contain a number of unique habitats utilizing nutrient poor, acidic soils. These globally rare habitats are most extensive in New Jersey, but extensive acreage also exists on Long Island, NY and

Nantucket Island, MA. A number of unique plant communities characterize the pitch pine/scrub oak barrens including scrub oak thickets (*Quercus* spp.), heathlands, sandplain grasslands, and pitch pine (*Pinus rigida*) woodlands. The habitat is well adapted to fire disturbance (Dunwiddie 1991) and periodical fire disturbance is required to maintain plant diversity.

The objectives of this study were to sample aboveground insects over one growing season on Nantucket in terrestrial plant communities that represent various habitats of the pitch pine/scrub oak barrens. At this point so little is known of habitat requirements for the majority of Nantucket's terrestrial insects, so the intention of this study was not strictly to assess management practices, but rather to begin understanding insect community structure within these habitats so that potential groups for monitoring may be identified for assessing management activities. The intention of this study is to compare insect communities at large (Order level) and small (species level) taxonomic groupings within each sampled habitats. In addition, seasonal patterns of arthropod abundance and diversity within these habitats will become apparent and may be useful for future sampling. Furthermore, as an improvement to the study by Dunwiddie (1991), I am concentrating on the beetle taxa at the species level to begin determining which species are widespread or restricted to specific habitats, but also to analyze faunal changes at the species level, rather than at broader taxonomic groupings, which may provide a more meaningful interpretation of how habitat management practices and plant community changes affect arthropod abundance. Finally, this study is also a part of an ongoing effort to produce an annotated checklist of the Coleoptera of Nantucket Island, which will further help to heighten our knowledge of the biodiversity on Nantucket.

Methods

Description of study area

The entire study area comprised seven sites located in a variety of habitats on Nantucket Island. Sites were selected on the criteria that they either coincided with the long-term biodiversity plots or that they represented a successional stage of a particular plant community. In each site, one 100m sampling transect was created and a GPS coordinate was taken and a flagged pole was placed at each end (Table 1). Because only one transect was placed within each site, transects were placed so that they ran directly through what appeared to be the characteristic composition of plant species for the site. For instance, I avoided as much as possible running transects through large, continuous stands of black huckleberry, scrub oak, bay berry, etc to capture a better diversity of plant species. In some cases this was unavoidable, but in these cases this was considered a correct representation of the plant community structure within a particular site.

Site descriptions

HB'03 (HB03)

Regenerating scrub oak thicket burned in 2003 (Figure 1). This site was composed of areas with dense areas of scrub (*Quercus illicifolia*) and chinquapin (*Quercus muehlenbergii*) oaks interspersed with dense ericaceous patches. Also within this mosaic were open patches dominated by bearberry (*Arctostaphylos uva-ursi*) and a few scattered pitch pines (*Pinus rigida*). Ericaceous plants included black huckleberry (*Gaylussacia baccata*), bayberry (*Myrica cerifera*), and low and high bush blueberry (*Vaccinium* spp.). Sweet fern (*Comptonia peregrina*) and other Compositae were sporadic as well as other remnant forest plants (wintergreen and lady slipper). The sampling transect began in an area with dense black huckleberry and sparse oak clumps for approximately the first 50m then it opened

up to an area with bare patches with fewer oak clumps and blueberry. The end of the sampling transect was in an area with very dense, 2m tall scrub/chinquapin oak clumps with small heaths patches.

Head of Plains (HPG)

Coastal sandplain grassland with small heath component (Figure 2). Transect proceeded east through areas dominated by little bluestem and other grasses (particularly *Carex*) with small, dense patches of black huckleberry and bayberry mixed throughout. Superficially, this site is similar the Smooth Hummocks grassland/heathland site (SMC), but differs due to a lesser abundance of ericaceous shrubs, *Rubus* sp., and scrub oak.

Milestone Road Mowed heathland (MRM)

A regenerating scrub oak thicket along Milestone Rd., which was annually mowed (Figures 3 and 4). This site has many of the same floral characteristics as HB'03, but differs in the size of scrub/chinquapin oaks, presence of large scattered sassafras, and abundance and sizes other ericaceous shrubs mainly due to the mowing regime. The distribution of vegetation along the transect included dense areas of scrub oak clumps intermixed with open patches dominated by bearberry, wintergreen (*Gaultheria procumbens*), and black huckleberry.

Pitch Pine canopy with scrub oak understory (PPSO)

This site was chosen because it is common on Nantucket and represents a successional stage that may support a unique community compared to other sites due to temperature difference caused by the canopy and composition of other plant species (Figure 5). I selected a site with a path running down the middle because this would allow for sweeping the vegetation without causing disruption before I sampled by walking along the transect. This transect was covered by a partial pitch pine canopy with an understory dominated by scrub oak. Vegetation along

the sides of the path where sweep net collections were taken included scrub oak (up to 1.5 m tall), dense stands of black huckleberry and high bush blueberry, sassafras, bayberry, *Viburnum*, pink lady's slipper (*Cypripedium acaule*), sweet fern, poison ivy (*Toxicodendron radicans*), and low bush blueberry.

Ram Pasture (RP)

Coastal sandplain grassland and heathland burned in fall of 2005. Transect is located near top of bluff and continued SW through graminoids (e.g *Carex*), low bush blueberry, bayberry, remaining stems and emerging black huckleberry, pasture rose (*Rosa*), St. John's Wort (*Hypericum*), and a yellow unidentified Compositae (Figure 6). The vegetation at this site, similar to Smooth Hummocks and relative to the others, was stunted and slower growing making early season sweep collections more difficult. Small, dense stands of black huckleberry were interspersed within low bush blueberry and grasses throughout the landscape.

Smooth Hummocks grassland/heathland (SMC)

Coastal sandplain grassland with greater heath component than the Head of the Plains site (Figure 7). Transect intersected through sections dominated by grasses, low bush blueberry, and areas with small, dense stands of black huckleberry. Other common plants included sweet fern (*Comptonia*), bayberry, raspberry (*Rubus*), and pasture rose (*Rosa* sp.). The transect was located on the east side of the dirt road running through the Miacomet Golf Course running south from Somerset Road about 0.5 mile down.

Smooth Hummocks Burned (SMB)

This site was located (~200m) southeast from the SMC site in an area that was burned in the spring 2005 (Figures 8 and 9). This site was similar in plant composition to the SMC site, but differed by having no dense stands of ericaceous shrubs (only their scorched remains left), not as densely covered with *Carex* sp.,

and with low lying areas with low bush blueberry and grasses. Little bluestem and *Rubus* were also quite more abundant along this transect than in SMC.

Arthropod sampling:

Aboveground arthropods were sampled at each site with a sweep net (diameter 30.4 cm) approximately every two weeks from 31 May until 9 September. On each sampling date for each site, three random samples were collected. The sample locations along each transect for each date was determined from a 10,000-digit random numbers table and were at least 10m apart for each sampling date. Each sample was collected by vigorously sweeping the vegetation 50 times in a back and forth motion through an area equal to approximately 5m². The contents of each sample were transferred to a labeled plastic bag and then placed into a cooler. Temperature at the time of sampling was recorded and cloud cover and wind speed were estimated at each site for each date. Cloud cover was estimated as 0 to 25% (clear), 25 to 75% (partly cloudy), and 75 to 100% (cloudy) cover and wind speed was estimated as calm or breezy. Twenty-one sweep samples were collected on each sampling date and samples were collected nine times from 31 May to 23 September, but not in each site (Table 1). For example, samples were collected on nine dates from 31 May to 23 September only in HB'03 and SMB (27 samples per site), eight dates from 15 June until 23 September only at HPG, PPSO, RP, SMC (24 samples per site). Finally, collections at MRM were restricted to only seven dates (21 samples), from 15 June until 23 September, but samples were not collected on 8 August because this site was mowed at this date. I was able to sample HB'03 and SMC on 31 May because vegetation was tall enough to sweep. I sampled during the same time of day and under similar weather conditions between sampling dates. Sweep net samples were removed from the cooler and placed in the freezer until arthropods were sorted to Class (Arachnida, Isopoda, Insecta) and Insecta to Order. Coleoptera were identified to species or separated into morphospecies using Downie and Arnett (1996), Arnett et

al. (2000, 2002), and Harpootlian (2001). All voucher specimens were placed in labeled vials with ~70-80% ethanol or pinned.

Data analysis

The mean temperature per date and per site over the entire season was calculated. The mean number of individuals per sample was calculated for each sampling date within each site. Species or Order/Class Richness (S), Shannon-Weiner Index (H'), Simpson's Index of Diversity, and Pielou's Evenness (J') were calculated over the entire season for each site. Simpson's index of diversity was calculated in addition to the Shannon-Weiner index because it provides a more intuitive meaning. For instance, the value of this index represents the probability that two individuals randomly selected from a sample will belong to different Classes/Orders. Between site comparisons of Coleoptera communities were made using Sorensen's quantitative similarity index (C_n). I also standardized the sweep data to adjust for the unequal number of samples taken between sites by excluding the samples taken on 31 May and 8/9 August 2005. I have presented both standardized and non-standardized diversity index values for all arthropods.

Between site and date effects on the collections of Arachnida, Coleoptera, Diptera, Hemiptera, Homoptera, Hymenoptera, Lepidoptera, and Orthoptera were log-transformed and analyzed using the GLM procedure in SAS (2002) by setting the categorical variables to site and order and including site, date, temperature, order, and site*order, site*date, and site*order interactions into the model. Between and within site differences for arthropod collections were analyzed using a multiple comparison test with Tukey's adjustment. Statistical significance was determined at the $\alpha = 0.05$ level.

Results

Sampling conditions

Temperature varied slightly over all sampling dates within each site (Figure 10), but temperature ($F= 66.55$; $df=1, 2439$; $P< 0.0001$) and the interaction of site and temperature ($F= 3.75$; $df=6, 2439$; $P= 0.001$) significantly affected arthropod collections in the model. PPSO recorded the lowest average temperature over the season while HPG and MRM recorded the highest average temperatures (Figure 10). Over all sites, the seasonal average temperature ranged from 68 to 89 degrees Fahrenheit and was highest on 22 August (Figure 11). The average temperature generally increased from the previous sampling date until 22 August (Figure 11). Wind speed and cloud cover at the earlier sampling dates were slightly cloudy and calm. From the end of June until the end of August most sampling dates were hot, humid, and calm with little or no cloud cover. The final two sampling dates (9 and 23 September) were breezy, but sunny and warm.

Arthropod collections

Class/Order level

A total of 9,360 individuals comprising three arthropod Classes (Arachnida, Insecta, and Isopoda) and within 15 insect Orders were collected in 171 samples taken in 2005 (Table 2 and Appendix I). In all samples Diptera (flies) were collected most frequently followed by Hymenoptera (wasps/ants/bees), Coleoptera (beetles), Homoptera (plant hoppers), Arachnida (Spiders), Lepidoptera (moths/butterflies), Hemiptera (true bugs), and finally Orthoptera (grasshoppers/crickets) (Table 2). When data was standardized, the total number of collected arthropods was 8,341 within three arthropod Classes and 12 insect Orders. For these data, again the Diptera were collected most frequently followed by Coleoptera, Hymenoptera, Homoptera, Arachnida, and Lepidoptera.

Diversity index values per site

Over all samples (unequal samples between sites) HB'03 collected the highest total number of arthropods (1,748) followed by HPG, SMC, PPSO, RP, MRM, and lastly SMB (Table 2). Most sites collected a similar number (richness) of Classes/insect Orders (between 11 and 13) except PPSO, which attained the highest richness 14 (Table 2). Shannon-Weiner (H') and Simpon's Index of diversity values at the Class/Order level were greatest in HB'03 followed by SMC, SMB, HPG, RP, PPSO, and MRM (Table 2). Evenness (J') was highest in HB'03 followed by SMB, SMC, RP, HPG, PPSO, and finally MRM.

Standardizing these data only slightly changed the diversity index site rankings. Collections were highest in HPG (1,516 individuals) followed by HB'03, SMC, PPSO, RP, SMB, and MRM (Table 1). Class/insect Order richness ranged from 11 to 13 between sites and HB'03, HPG, MRM, and SMC all recorded a richness value equal to 13 (Table 1). The ranking of sites based on the Shannon-Wiener and Simpon's index of diversity values varied only slightly between the total and standardized data. For instance, the only difference was the position of RP relative to HPG, where RP attained a higher H' value than HPG, but both had equal Simpon's values; both were still less than HB'03, SMC, and SMB (Table 1). Finally, evenness values (J') followed virtually the same pattern as the non-standardized data, where HB'03 had the greatest value and MRM or PPSO lowest. The only difference to the non-standardized data was that evenness in MRM and PPSO were equal, as were RP and SMC (Table 1).

Collections of arthropods were significantly affected by site ($F= 4.10$; $df=6$, 2439; $P< 0.0001$), date ($F= 223.35$; $df=1$, 2439; $P< 0.0001$), and the interaction of data and site ($F= 15.33$; $df=6$, 2439; $P< 0.0001$). HPG collected the highest mean number of arthropods per sample followed by HB'03, SMC, PPSO, RP, MRM, and SMB (Figure 12). The results of Tukey's test determined that collections were similar within the following site groupings (1) HPG, HB'03, SMC, and PPSO, (2)

HB'03, SMC, PPSO, and RP, (3) RP and MRM, and (4) MRM and SMB (Figure 12).

Samples taken on 27 June collected the highest total (1,935) number of arthropods and the highest Class/Order richness (Table 3). Samples collected on 23 September collected the lowest total (264) of all dates and the samples taken on the 8/9 August collected the lowest Class/Order richness (Table 3). Each site generally displayed one peak in arthropod abundance between 27 June and 26 July (Figure 13). However, HPG, RP, and SMB had two peaks (Figure 13). Peak collections in HB'03 and HPG were higher earlier in the season compared to all other sites and samples taken within these sites steadily declined after this peak. Seasonal arthropod abundance in MRM displayed a similar pattern to HB'03 and HPG with a corresponding peak abundance period, but the total abundance was generally lower over the entire season. In addition, a drastic reduction in abundance from 180 to 38 individuals was observed in MRM before and after mowing that occurred on 8 and 9 August (Figure 13). Seasonal abundance at RP was consistently lower than most sites. After the initial peak collection on 27 June, the following samples captured similar numbers of arthropods over next four sample dates until another sudden peak on 8 September (Figure 13). Total arthropod abundance in PPSO was moderate compared to all sites for most dates (except 27 June) and peaked on 26 July (288 individuals). SMC followed a similar pattern of arthropod seasonal abundance to PPSO. Both sites had a corresponding peak collection date with a gradual increase and decrease surrounding this peak (Figure 13). Finally, collections at SMB were generally lower than all other sites over the season, except around the two very distinct peaks similar to those observed at RP, but not exactly corresponding to the same dates as in RP (Figure 13).

Site had a significant effect on the abundance of a particular Order/Class. For instance, the mean number of Arachnida were similar in HB'03, SMC, PPSO,

HPG, but of these sites only HB'03 and SMC collected a significantly higher number of spiders than in MRM and SMB (Figure 14A). Diptera were collected most frequently in SMC and RP and significantly more than in MRM and PPSO (Figure 14C). The rank order of the abundance of Homoptera and Hymenoptera relative to site followed a similar pattern to one another. For example, the greatest abundance of each Order was recorded in RP followed by MRM, SMC, PPSO, HPG, SMB, and finally HB'03 (Figure 14 E & F). A significantly greater number of Homoptera were collected in all other sites excluding MRM (Figure 14E). For the Hymenoptera, similar collections were made between RP, MRM, SMC and PPSO and PPSO, HPG, and HB'03 (Figure 14F). There was no difference in collections of Coleoptera, Hemiptera, Lepidoptera, and Orthoptera between sites (Figure 14C, D, G, and H). The highest mean number of Coleoptera, Hemiptera, and Lepidoptera was collected in SMC and Orthoptera was collected most frequently in SMB.

Peak periods of abundance of each Class/Order per site

The peak in Arachnida activity occurred from 8/9 to 8 September over all sites and steadily increased after the 26 July collection until it began to decrease into mid-September (Table 3). The majority of sites displayed a similar seasonal pattern of Arachnida abundance with a mid to late season peak except for in SMB and MRM where collections were reduced compared to the other sites and only a gradual increase in abundance was observed over the season (Figure 15A). Peak abundance of Coleoptera was observed from 15 June until 26 July over all sites (Table 3) and all but PPSO displayed a peak period in beetle activity during this period (Figure 15B). Both HPG and SMB displayed sharp peaks in abundance most likely corresponding to peaks in a particular species peak emergence period. After the samples taken on 26 July Coleoptera abundance decreased rapidly and continuously over the remainder of the collection period (Figure 15B). The

abundance of Diptera did not show a consistent trend between sites over the sampling season (Figure 15C), but collections of Diptera were high from mid-June until early September (Table 3). Peak collections of Diptera at HB'03, HPG, MRM, and PPSO were earlier in the season (16 and 27 June), in the middle of the season for SMC (26 July), and later in the season for SMB and RP (Figure 15C). The seasonal abundance of Hemiptera was generally characterized by a relatively low abundance (Table 3) with no remarkable peaks except in HB'03 (Figure 15D). In HB'03 a large peak in abundance occurred starting on 28 June, peaked on 12 July and ended between late July early August (Figure 15D). Peak abundance of Homoptera occurred on 26 July in MRM and SMC, 27 June in RP and HPG, and 11 July in HB'03 and PPSO (Figure 15E). Homoptera collections peaked during the late season in SMB, which also corresponded to the second noticeable peak that occurred at HPG (Figure 14E). Peak abundance of Hymenoptera was similar to most other groups with an early season peak, but the seasonal abundance of Hymenoptera differed most notably from the other groups with the highest abundance in PPSO during the middle of the sampling period (Figure 15F). The seasonality of Lepidoptera was comparable to Hemiptera, where a large peak in abundance occurred at HB'03 over a narrow period of time (Figure 15G). Finally, collections of Orthoptera were relatively low and did not display similar peaks in abundance between many sites (Figure H). For most sites, abundance gradually decreased over the season but was just the opposite in HPG where abundance peaked early and decreased over the season (Figure 15H).

Finally, arthropod collections taken in MRM before (26 July-180 individuals) and then after (22 August-38 individuals) the mowing event on 8 August showed an 80% reduction in total abundance. The most notable reductions occurred within the Coleoptera (91%) (Figure 15B, black line), Diptera (84%) (Figure 15C, black line), Hymenoptera (86%) (Figure 15F, black line), and Homoptera (48%) (Figure 15E, black line). Because of its structural similarity

and comparable plant community to MRM, HB'03 may be useful site for assessing the affects of mowing activities to the aboveground arthropods in MRM. In HB'03 total abundance reduced by 31% for all arthropods, 65% for Coleoptera, 83% for Diptera, 55% for Homoptera, and an increase of 37% occurred for Hymenoptera from 26 July until 22 August (Figure 15).

Coleoptera collections

A total of 1,797 beetles comprising 101 morphospecies within 32 families were collected in sweep net samples (Table 4). The highest abundance of beetles was recorded from SMC followed by MRM, HPG, HB'03, RP, SMB, and finally PPSO (Table 4). Samples collected in PPSO were most diverse at the family (27 families) and species level (40 species) and this site attained the highest H', Simpson's Index of diversity, and evenness values of all sites (Table 4). On the other hand, the lowest diversity of beetles was observed in SMB and RP, where in each site 14 families were collected comprising 22 and 23 species, respectively (Table 4). Samples taken on 27 June collected the highest abundance (540) and species diversity (52 species) of Coleoptera (Table 3). Beetle diversity at the family and species level was greatest during the period from 15/16 June to 26 July (Appendix X). Samples taken on 26 July collected the highest family level diversity (24) (Appendix X). The lowest abundance (20) and species diversity (9 species) was recorded from samples taken on 23 September, but samples from 8 September were also very low (Figure 15B & Appendix X).

The most dominant beetle families over all sites were Chrysomelidae (45.5%), Tenebrionidae (10.5%), and Cantharidae (10.1%) (Table 4). The most commonly collected species were the chrysomelids *Triachus atomus* (Suffrian) (21.4%) and *Altica* sp. (10.4%) and the cantharid *Cantharis* sp. 1 (9.2%) (Cantharidae) (Appendices III-VIII). Chrysomelidae were the most abundant beetle family collected in HB'03, HPG, MRM, and RP, the Mycetophagidae

dominated samples in PPSO, Cantharidae (e.g. *Cantharis* spp.) in SMC, and finally the Tenebrionidae (e.g. *Isomira* sp.) were the most abundant in SMB.

Calculation of Sorensen's quantitative index (Cn) for assessing the similarity of sites based on Coleoptera species composition and abundance determined that the beetle community within RP and MRM were most similar (Table 5). HB'03 and RP and HB'03 and MRM attained the next highest similarity index values. Beetle communities in MRM and SMB were the least similar (Table 5).

Discussion

The intention of this study was to sample above ground arthropods in Nantucket's major terrestrial habitat types in order to begin describing the arthropod assemblages in each habitat, identify peak periods of activity of insect groups and beetle species, and to collect insect community data which may be useful for assessing the affects of habitat management to the entire biological community. In addition, by sampling these arthropods I intended to determine which sites shared similar arthropod communities. A better understanding of how each habitat type affects insect community structure (e.g. plant species and phenology) and the identification of habitats that support similar insect assemblages, may play an important role in future management. For instance, if we can identify and preserve habitats serving as refugia for some species, these species may be able to re-colonize areas after a disturbance event. In addition, by combining this information with floral community data a better understanding of how plant community structure within these sites affects arthropod diversity and vice versa will begin to unfold and better direct management activities. Finally, I focused on Coleoptera taxa because of the diverse habits they have and because they typically play a large role in major ecological processes. My intention of this report is not to go into great detail about beetle diversity on Nantucket. For this purpose, the assemblages of beetles and their ecological functions will be discussed rather than extensive reports of new species records, etc.

Total arthropod collections

The results of sweep netting indicated that HB'03 and HPG supported the highest abundance and diversity of arthropods over the entire sampling season of all sites although HPG and HB'03 did not record the highest seasonal average value for any of the particular arthropod groups analyzed. The only exception was in HB'03, where Arachnida were most abundant over the entire season at this site. SMC was particularly interesting in that four arthropod groups (Coleoptera, Diptera, Hemiptera, and Lepidoptera) were collected the most frequently at this site per sample over the entire season and I should point out that the Diptera and Coleoptera were among the most abundant taxa collected. SMC also recorded the third highest mean number of arthropods per sample. These observations indicate that the aboveground arthropod community inhabiting SMC was the most diverse of the sites sampled.

Interestingly, although the abundance and diversity at HPG was relatively high, no arthropod groups displayed any particular preference for HPG as indicated by the mean number collected per sample over the entire season. For example, over all of the arthropod groups considered, HPG ranked in the middle of sites with the exception of the Hemiptera. Another interesting observation was that similar to HPG, HB'03 collected a relatively high diversity and abundance of arthropods. But, compared to the other sites, the lowest collections of Homoptera, Lepidoptera, and Hymenoptera were collected in HB'03. Finally, a similar trend was observed in SMB, but in just the opposite fashion. In SMB, which was characterized by the lowest abundance and diversity of all sites, the Orthoptera were most abundant throughout the sampling season.

It became clear that some habitats supported richer arthropod assemblages than others and some habitats supported specific taxonomic groups. However, at this point it is difficult to discern how the actual plant community affected these taxa because little is known of the biology of these organisms. Further taxonomic

resolution past the Order level and ideally to the species level would begin to help analyze the interrelationships between plant and arthropod communities. This information would be useful in determining which habitats may act as areas for arthropods to disperse out of to re-colonize new areas.

By sweep net sampling over such a long period I was able to determine that abundance of aboveground arthropods was highest from the middle of June until mid-July and this corresponded to the peak period in abundance and diversity of the majority of taxa. Of the 14 distinct taxa collected, eight displayed peak collections during this collection period. It also became apparent that each arthropod group had a specific time period during the season where they were most abundant as adults. However, the only exception were the Diptera, which displayed a fairly consistent abundance over the entire season. Most groups displayed an early season emergence and a gradual decrease in abundance past 26 July, although late season peaks in abundance were observed for the Arachnida, Diptera, and Orthoptera. For the Arachnida, a higher abundance later in the season most likely occurs due to the population buildup of prey species. There was no consistent trend in seasonality of the major herbivore taxa (Homoptera, Orthoptera, and some Coleoptera) between sites, so it is difficult to say at this point what site attributes affect their abundance, possibly the stage of plant growth.

Clearly, arthropod collections were depressed in the sites receiving management in 2005 (MRM, RP, and SMB), but some groups were actually quite abundant in these sites compared to the others. The major insect Orders and the Arachnids were all generally collected less frequently within at least one of the managed sites except for the Coleoptera. In fact, these three sites were among the top four sites in terms of the average number of beetles per sample over the season. However, it is difficult to interpret these results and suggest that management was the casual factor because even the most diverse and abundant sites still collected the lowest average number of particular taxa (e.g. HB'03).

The reduction in arthropod abundance observed after the mowing event in MRM was large, but an important point to consider is the natural decrease in abundance of arthropods during this time period. However, in HB'03, which is by far the most comparable site in terms of plant community similarity to MRM, showed a reduction in abundance of only 31% compared to 80% in MRM during the same period. Therefore, it is difficult to ignore that mowing may have drastically altered abundance. Light trap collections taken before and after mowing at MRM have also demonstrated a drastic reduction in the abundance of Lepidoptera and Scarabaeidae (Mello & Weed 2006). Furthermore, pitfall trapping within MRM has determined that complete changes in beetle species composition and, for most groups, a reduction in their abundance occurs following mowing. But, some groups also show a remarkable increase in their abundance after mowing (e.g. Scarabaeinae) (Weed & Mello 2006).

Coleoptera collections

The beetle assemblages within the sampled habitats were composed mainly of herbivores (e.g. Chrysomelidae, Atellabidae, Curculionidae, and Anthribidae) but also predators (e.g. Cleridae and Cantharidae) were quite abundant. As mentioned previously, the major peak in beetle abundance occurred during late June until mid-July. This peak in adult abundance also corresponded to the time when the highest diversity of beetles occurred. PPSO supported the highest beetle diversity. Of the 29 morphospecies that were collected once during the season in all samples, 10 were collected only in PPSO. In addition, 17 species and 7 families were exclusive to this site. This suggests that PPSO contains a number of species that may not be widespread on Nantucket and may be restricted to this habitat type. For example, the nemonychid *Cimberis pilosus* LeConte, which has never been reported from Nantucket before this study, is apparently a specialist feeder on pollen of *Pinus* spp. Another rare record for the island collected in PPSO was the eucnemid *Deltometopus amoenicornis* (Say). Only one specimen of this species

has been collected by me in the previous summer and was also in a pitch pine dominated forest. These are indications that some members of the beetle community and perhaps other invertebrate groups are unique to the pitch pine forests on Nantucket. The occurrence of species found exclusively in PPSO was expected due to the differences in plant communities and structural growth differences; however, the high species diversity was not.

The beetle communities within the remainder of sites (HB'03, HPG, MRM, RP, SMB, and SMC) were not as distinctive as that of PPSO. For example, HB'03 was the only site where one family (Scritidae) was exclusively collected and each of the other sites yielded few unique species. Many species were shared between sites, but this did not suggest that many sites had similar beetle communities. This was reflected by the Sorensen's quantitative similarity index (C_n) values, which calculates similarity as an index on a scale from 0 (dissimilar) to 1 (similar) based upon the abundance of each species. Following this index, RP and MRM were most similar followed by RP and HB'03, HB'03 and MRM, RP and HPG, and SMC and SMB. On the other hand, SMB and MRM were the least similar followed by HPG and HB'03, and RP and SMB. The implications of these results should be interpreted cautiously because of the sampling strategy. However, the index insinuates some interesting conclusions. For example, I would have expected HB'03 and MRM to support very similar beetle assemblages. This was because both sites are close together, very similar in plant community structure, and are quite distant if not isolated from the remainder of sites excluding PPSO. Also, because of the generally low diversity and abundance observed during the beginning of August in both sites it seems likely that a late season mowing event in MRM would not have affected this index value greatly.

HPG and SMC were interesting sites for collections of beetles because abundance and diversity was high at these sites and I will consider them together due to their close proximity and similar species composition of plants. RP could

also be included here also because it is located on the southern coast of Nantucket and is comprised of similar plant species, but I will discuss this site within the context of the managed sites. Both HPG and SMC generally collected similar beetle species with a few exceptions. For example, 45 species were collected in both sites, but 13 (29%) of these species were only collected in HPG whereas only 9% were collected only in SMC. The question remains why did HPG support such a higher unique assemblage of species compared to SMC? Another interesting observation was that some species displayed remarkable differences in abundances between these sites. The most striking instance of this was the copper-colored flea-beetle *Altica* sp. where 151 individuals were collected in HPG and only one swept from SMC. Also, *Trigonorhinus rotundatus* (LeConte), a seed head feeder of black huckleberry, was very abundant in SMC, but not HPG. All of these observations may reflect actual differences between plant communities of these sites, but at this point it is difficult to say because the distribution of these organisms in the sites is not well understood.

As mentioned previously, total beetle abundance within sites that received some type of recent disturbance were neither depressed nor less diverse than the other sites. However, there were notable differences in the abundances of Anthribidae, Atellabidae, Cantharidae, Chrysomelidae, Phalacridae, and Tenebrionidae that occurred between SMC and SMB (Table 7). *Phalacrus politus* Melsheimer, *Triachus cerinus* LeConte, *T. atomus*, *Cantharis* sp., and *Trigonorhinus rotundatus*, were all extremely abundant in SMC, but only occasionally swept in the SMB site. Abundance of *Isomira* sp. on the other hand was just the opposite, where it was over three times as common in SMB than SMC. I think the best explanation for the overall lower abundance in SMB could have been due to the lack of plant material available for consumption and cover caused by the fire.

The beetle diversity of RP and SMB were very similar, but the C_n index suggested that these sites were very dissimilar. This was because of high collections of different species at each site. It appears that the spring fire disturbance at RP may have affected many taxa similar to SMB, but apparently had no large effect on *Triachus atomus*, which accounted for 55% of the total numbers of beetle. It would be interesting to sample this site in the future to monitor population changes and to determine whether surrounding habitats act as refugia to this site. Samples taken of ground-dwelling arthropods over 2004 to 2005 have indicated that many rare species appear to be restricted to RP and may suffer initially from the burn, but rebound quickly even within the same season (Weed & Mello 2006). Without having sampled prior to burning it is hard to determine whether the same is true of the aboveground arthropods, in particular the herbivores.

Conclusion

In this report I have summarized the sweep sampling data into a variety of insect diversity measures that are commonly used for describing community structure of biological organisms. Because this represents the first year of sampling it is difficult to insinuate much more than to just report and comment on site comparisons based on the diversity indices, between sites and state how the phenology of insect fauna was affected per site. The breadth of information that was reported in this study resulted from the large number of samples taken over the entire season within these sites and a great deal of taxonomic work. Such extensive sampling was taken mainly to capture a large number of species and to identify peaks in abundance. I feel that this sampling strategy has done this quite well. Numerous taxa were documented from each habitat and some species of beetle were newly recorded. However, the downfalls of such sampling are that it is difficult to identify all taxa to a level that provides meaningful information for practical application. In many ways this study sets the stage for future research

that can be useful for biodiversity and habitat management on Nantucket. Furthermore, this study has highlighted many interesting patterns of the aboveground insect communities on Nantucket. First, it was apparent that many insect groups and beetle species inhabit the coastal heathland/grassland communities that have been identified as major biodiversity study sites on Nantucket and at some level their diversity is similar. Second, pitch pine forested sites on Nantucket boast a unique fauna compared to the open habitats, so it would be interesting in the future to compare the assemblages of other forest types to determine whether their communities are also unique. I have begun investigating this with the ground dwelling fauna already. Third, seasonality of the aboveground arthropods varied slightly between sites, but for the most part is synchronized. Other than the interesting environmental factors that are affecting arthropod phenology, this information is very useful when initiating targeted sampling of particular groups. Fourth, it is apparent that many of the aboveground arthropod communities are composed of herbivores. The large number of predators collected suggests that these herbivores are potentially important prey so any disturbance or alteration to these habitats that impacts the herbivores may have profound affects on the entire food chain. One major outcome from a change in the food web could be loss of productive bird foraging habitat.

Future Prospects

The results of this study and the many organisms collected has spawned an interest to begin extending this type of sampling method to other habitats on Nantucket purely for documentation of biodiversity and to make records of habitat interactions of species. Although my primary interest and experience lies with the Coleoptera, this sampling method also proves effective for collecting many other taxa that could be valuable specimens for specialists to examine sometime in the future. As an improvement to this study and to produce data that can be applicable to biodiversity conservation, I would like to continue sampling in the coastal

heathland/grassland habitats, but instead of many samples taken over time and in many habitats, I would like to restrict sampling to a defined, shorter period but intensify the number of samples taken within each habitat. This strategy is superior because I will be able to estimate within site distribution and also will be able to concentrate on fewer plant communities and begin determining which insects feed on which plant species. This type of data collection lends itself to stronger statistical analyses and thus provides more informative results. Then, this information can be used for predicting future population trends in the face of disturbances, such as fire or mowing management.

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Tables

Table 1. Site location and sweep sample collection dates for 2005.

Site ID	Site Abbrev.	Transect Coordinates		Sampling dates								
		0m	100m									
HB03- Middle Moors	HB'03	N 41 16'53.4" W 70 01'52.9"	N 41 16'51.1" W 70 01'54.8"	31-May	15-Jun	27-Jun	11-Jul	26-Jul	8-Aug	23-Aug	8-Sep	23-Sep
Head of the Plains Grassland	HPG	N 41 15'48.8" W 70 10'10.6"	N 41 15'49.6" W 70 10'07.0"		16-Jun	27-Jun	12-Jul	26-Jul	9-Aug	23-Aug	8-Sep	23-Sep
Milestone Rd. Mowed	MRM	N 41 15'50.9" W 70 01'11.7"	N 41 15'52.6" W 70 01'11.5"		16-Jun	27-Jun	11-Jul	26-Jul	9-Aug	23-Aug	8-Sep	23-Sep
Pitch pine/ SO understory	PPSO	N 41 15'47.6" W 70 01'18.1"	N 41 15'44.8" W 70 01'12.9"		16-Jun	27-Jun	11-Jul	26-Jul	9-Aug	23-Aug	8-Sep	23-Sep
Ram Pasture	RP	N 41 15'31.5" W 70 09'43.8"	N 41 15'29.1" W 70 09'41.6"		16-Jun	27-Jun	12-Jul	26-Jul	9-Aug	23-Aug	8-Sep	23-Sep
Smooth Hummocks Burned	SMB	N 41 15'01.5" W 70 07'21.1"	N 41 15'00.3" W 70 07'17.0"		16-Jun	27-Jun	11-Jul	26-Jul	9-Aug	23-Aug	8-Sep	23-Sep
Smooth Hummocks Control	SMC	N 41 15'03.5" W 70 07'27.3"	N 41 15'05.1" W 70 07'30.3"	31-May	16-Jun	27-Jun	11-Jul	26-Jul	9-Aug	23-Aug	8-Sep	23-Sep

Table 2. Total number of arthropods collected per site in 2005. Diversity index values in parentheses represent standardized data (see Methods section for explanation.)

Class or Insect Order	HB03	HPG	MRM	PPSO	RP	SMB	SMC	Total	% Total
ARACHNIDA ^b	233	173	75	190	89	39	223	1022	10.92%
BLATTARIA	3	2	3	7	0	0	0	15	0.16%
COLEOPTERA ^b	254	328	334	122	213	187	359	1797	19.20%
COLLEMBOLA	88	4	25	1	120	72	47	357	3.81%
DIPTERA ^b	345	516	125	264	471	97	232	2050	21.90%
HEMIPTERA ^b	51	6	4	11	3	2	11	88	0.94%
HOMOPTERA ^b	314	309	73	111	88	146	323	1364	14.57%
HYMENOPTERA ^b	221	161	379	550	140	142	220	1813	19.37%
ISOPODA	0	0	0	9	0	1	3	13	0.14%
LEPIDOPTERA ^b	175	58	31	99	59	35	54	511	5.46%
MANTODEA	0	3	0	0	0	1	1	5	0.05%
MECOPTERA	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	2	0.02%
NEUROPTERA	3	1	1	6	0	0	0	11	0.12%
ORTHOPTERA ^b	27	64	4	10	21	14	49	189	2.02%
PSOCOPTERA	5	0	2	0	0	0	4	11	0.12%
THYSANOPTERA	6	5	19	3	1	2	13	49	0.52%
TRICHOPTERA	0	0	0	0	3	0	0	3	0.03%
COLEOPTERA LARVAE ^a	11	0	0	3	1	0	21	36	0.38%
UNKNOWN ^a	12	1	2	4	0	4	1	24	0.26%
Total	1748 (1459)	1631 (1516)	1077 (1077)	1392 (1243)	1209 (1100)	742 (683)	1561 (1263)	9360 (8341)	
Class/Order Richness (S)	13 (13)	13 (13)	13 (13)	14 (13)	11 (11)	12 (12)	13 (13)	14	
Shannon's Diversity (H')	2.11 (2.10)	1.80 (1.77)	1.70 (1.69)	1.77 (1.71)	1.79 (1.80)	1.93 (1.88)	2.00 (1.93)		
Simpson's Index	0.86 (0.86)	0.80 (0.80)	0.75 (0.76)	0.77 (0.77)	0.78 (0.80)	0.83 (0.76)	0.84 (0.84)		
Evenness (J') all dates	0.82 (0.82)	0.70 (0.69)	0.66 (0.66)	0.67 (0.66)	0.75 (0.75)	0.78 (0.76)	0.78 (0.75)		

^a Taxa not included in calculation of diversity values and in the statistical analysis

^b Taxa included in the statistical analysis

Table 3. Summary of arthropods collected per date in sweep net samples in 2005.

Class or Insect Order	Sample Date									Total	% Total
	31-May	15/16-Jun	27-Jun	11/12-Jul	26-Jul	8/9 Aug	22-Aug	8-Sep	23-Sep		
ARACHNIDA ^b	39	13	91	12	87	131	229	133	89	1022	10.9%
BLATTARIA	1	1	2	1	4	3	3	0	0	15	0.2%
COLEOPTERA ^b	25	372	540	469	195	99	55	22	20	1797	19.2%
COLLEMBOLA	31	1	26	19	35	18	54	158	15	357	3.8%
DIPTERA ^b	26	392	495	276	321	192	181	14	27	2050	21.9%
HEMIPTERA ^b	0	7	11	35	17	7	9	1	1	88	0.9%
HOMOPTERA ^b	13	84	227	229	272	19	239	74	36	1364	14.6%
HYMENOPTERA ^b	43	368	372	381	34	19	167	38	31	1813	19.4%
ISOPODA	0	0	12	0	0	0	0	1	0	13	0.1%
LEPIDOPTERA ^b	1	28	118	123	74	32	62	45	28	511	5.5%
MANTODEA	0	0	0	0	0	0	4	1	0	5	0.1%
MECOPTERA	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	2	0.0%
NEUROPTERA	0	1	1	0	2	0	0	0	7	11	0.1%
ORTHOPTERA ^b	4	17	33	27	37	23	34	5	9	189	2.0%
PSOCOPTERA	0	0	0	0	0	0	5	6	0	11	0.1%
THYSANOPTERA	3	9	7	11	14	0	5	0	0	49	0.5%
TRICHOPTERA	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	0	3	0.0%
COLEOPTERA LARVAE ^a	19	0	0	5	6	2	1	2	1	36	0.4%
UNKNOWN ^a	0	0	0	3	4	3	7	7	0	24	0.3%
Total	205	1383	1935	1700	1372	809	1056	636	264	9360	
Class/Order Richness	9	12	13	10	10	8	12	11	9		

^a Taxa not included in diversity calculations and statistical analysis

^b Taxa included in statistical analysis

Table 4. Family level abundance and diversity of Coleoptera in sweep net samples per site.

Family	HB03	HPG	MRM	PPSO	RP	SMB	SMC	Total	% Total
ADERIDAE	0	0	4	2	0	0	0	6	0.33%
ANOBIIDAE	1	0	0	1	2	0	0	4	0.22%
ANTHRIBIDAE	0	5	0	0	0	0	46	51	2.84%
ATELLABIDAE	25	4	16	12	4	1	16	78	4.34%
BRENTIDAE	0	9	0	6	0	8	3	26	1.45%
BRUCHIDAE	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	2	0.11%
BUPRESTIDAE	7	3	21	5	1	2	5	44	2.45%
CANTHARIDAE	19	16	1	3	1	17	125	182	10.13%
CARABIDAE	9	1	0	0	2	0	2	14	0.78%
CHRYSOMELIDAE	93	241	214	5	176	19	69	817	45.46%
CLERIDAE	28	4	37	2	1	2	2	76	4.23%
COCCINELLIDAE	25	10	4	4	7	3	4	57	3.17%
CORYLOPHIDAE	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0.06%
CURCULIONIDAE	14	7	2	22	4	13	4	66	3.67%
ELATERIDAE	3	2	6	6	0	3	3	23	1.28%
EUCNEMIDAE	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0.06%
LAMPYRIDAE	0	0	0	1	0	0	2	3	0.17%
LATRIDIIDAE	5	3	4	2	0	1	1	16	0.89%
LYCIDAE	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0.06%
MELANDRYIDAE	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	2	0.11%
MELYRIDAE	4	3	0	1	6	0	0	14	0.78%
MORDELLIDAE	2	0	7	1	0	1	0	11	0.61%
MYCETOPHAGIDAE	0	1	0	24	2	0	1	28	1.56%
NEMONYCHIDAE	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0.06%
NITIDULIDAE	0	0	0	1	0	2	0	3	0.17%
PHALACRIDAE	0	11	0	0	1	1	41	54	3.01%
SCARABAEIDAE	0	4	14	0	1	0	0	19	1.06%
SCIRTIDAE	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0.06%
SCYDMAENIDAE	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0.06%
STAPHYLINIDAE	2	0	0	2	0	0	0	4	0.22%
TENEBRIONIDAE	16	4	3	12	5	114	35	189	10.52%
THROSCIDAE	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	2	0.11%
Total	254	328	334	122	213	187	359	1797	
Family Richness	16	17	14	27	14	14	16	32	
Species Richness	34	38	30	40	23	22	34	101	
Shannon's Diversity (H')	2.13	1.25	1.35	2.58	0.87	1.46	1.66		
Simpson's Index of Diversity	0.82	0.45	0.57	0.90	0.33	0.60	0.80		
Evenness (J')	0.77	0.44	0.51	0.78	0.31	0.55	0.60		

Table 5. Sorensen's quantitative similarity index (Cn) matrix based on Coleoptera species data between sites. Higher values indicate sites with more similar beetle communities.

Site	HB03	HPG	MRM	PPSO	RP	SMB	SMC
HB03		0.062	0.418	0.245	0.433	0.150	0.189
HPG	0.062		0.196	0.098	0.318	0.151	0.239
MRM	0.418	0.196		0.110	0.574	0.042	0.084
PPSO	0.245	0.098	0.110		0.096	0.104	0.116
RP	0.433	0.318	0.574	0.096		0.070	0.119
SMB	0.150	0.151	0.042	0.104	0.070		0.264
SMC	0.189	0.239	0.084	0.116	0.119	0.264	

Figures

Figure 1. HB'03 transect looking from 0m 14 June 2005.

Figure 2. HPG transect looking from 0m 16 June 2005.

Figure 3. MRM transect looking from 0m on 26 July 2006. Before annual mow.

Figure 4. MRM site after 8-9 August 2005 annual mow.

Figure 5. PPSO transect along path looking from 0m on to 100m on 26 July 2005.

Figure 6. Location of Ram Pasture transect looking roughly from 0m on 26 July 2006.

Figure 7. Location of SMC transect looking from 0m on 11 July 2005.

Figure 8. Location of SMB transect looking from 0m on 31 May 2005.

Figure 9. Location of SMB transect looking from 0m on 11 July 2005.

Figure 10. Average temperature (°F) (±SD) per sampling date for each site.

Figure 11. Average temperature per sampling date over the season.

Figure 12. Mean number of arthropods collected per sample in each site over the season. Letters represent the results of the lsmeans procedure between sites for each Class/Order. Sites with the same letters are similar at the $\alpha = 0.05$ level.

Figure 13. Total number of arthropods per date within each site. Sample number on x-axis corresponds to the following dates. 1= 31 May, 2= 15/16 June, 3= 27 June, 4= 11/12 July, 5= 26 July, 6= 8/9 August, 7= 22 August, 8= 8 September, and 9= 23 September.

Figure 14. Mean number of arthropods collected per sample in each site for (A) Arachnida, (B) Coleoptera, (C) Diptera, (D) Hemiptera, (E) Homoptera, (F) Hymenoptera, (G) Lepidoptera, and (H) Orthoptera. Letters represent the results of the lsmeans procedure between sites for each Class/Order. Sites with the same letters are similar at the $\alpha=0.05$ level.

Appendix Tables

Appendix I. Total number of insects Orders and other invertebrate Classes collected in sweep samples during 2005

Site	Order	31-May-05	15-Jun-05	27-Jun-05	11-Jul-05	26-Jul-05	8-Aug-05	22-Aug-05	8-Sep-05	23-Sep-05	Grand Total	
HB03	Arachnida	24	22	19	32	20	50	21	30	15	233	
	Blattaria	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	3	
	Coleoptera	15	48	92	50	20	15	7	4	3	254	
	Coleoptera larva	4	0	0	0	3	2	1	1	0	11	
	Collembola	29	0	1	5	0	0	0	50	3	88	
	Diptera	9	40	103	84	56	39	10	3	1	345	
	Hemiptera	0	2	6	29	11	2	1	0	0	51	
	Homoptera	10	21	50	65	53	48	24	37	6	314	
	Hymenoptera	14	29	53	53	23	14	37	10	5	221	
	Lepidoptera	1	1	69	91	2	4	2	2	3	175	
	Neuroptera	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	3	
	Orthoptera	3	2	2	7	8	2	3	0	0	27	
	Psocoptera	0	0	0	0	0	0	5	0	0	5	
	Thysanoptera	1	2	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	6	
	Unknown	0	0	0	0	0	1	7	4	0	12	
	Grand Total		111	168	379	417	198	178	118	141	38	1748
HPG	Order	31-May-05	16-Jun-05	27-Jun-05	12-Jul-05	26-Jul-05	9-Aug-05	22-Aug-05	8-Sep-05	23-Sep-05	Grand Total	
	Arachnida		16	24	18	13	27	58	5	12	173	
	Blattaria		0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	2	
	Coleoptera		60	68	157	19	16	6	1	1	328	
	Collembola		1	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	1	
	Diptera		157	172	22	71	25	63	4	2	516	
	Hemiptera		2	3	0	1	0	0	0	0	6	
	Homoptera		26	90	50	46	28	58	4	7	309	
	Hymenoptera		31	49	19	22	4	27	4	5	161	
	Lepidoptera		9	13	6	14	7	9	0	0	58	
	Mantodea		0	0	0	0	0	2	1	0	3	
	Neuroptera		0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	
	Orthoptera		5	17	9	11	8	5	2	7	64	
	Thysanoptera		2	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	5	
	Unknown		0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	
	Grand Total		0	309	439	281	200	115	228	24	35	1631
MRM	Order	31-May-05	16-Jun-05	27-Jun-05	11-Jul-05	26-Jul-05	9-Aug-05	22-Aug-05	8-Sep-05	23-Sep-05	Grand Total	
	Arachnida		17	10	22	13		8	2	3	75	
	Blattaria		1	2	0	2	0	0	0	0	4	
	Coleoptera		39	100	134	55		5	1	0	334	
	Collembola		0	4	13	0		0	6	2	25	
	Diptera		36	38	20	25		4	0	2	125	
	Hemiptera		0	1	2	1		0	0	0	4	
	Homoptera		6	10	18	21		11	2	5	73	
	Hymenoptera		95	121	104	49		7	3	0	379	
	Lepidoptera		4	10	8	4		2	2	1	31	
	Neuroptera		0	0	0	0		0	0	1	1	
	Orthoptera		2	1	0	1		0	0	0	4	
	Psocoptera		0	0	0	0		0	2	0	2	
	Thysanoptera		5	2	1	10		1	0	0	19	
	Unknown		0	0	1	1		0	0	0	2	
	Grand Total		0	205	299	323	180	0	38	18	14	1077
PPSO	Order	31-May-05	16-Jun-05	27-Jun-05	11-Jul-05	26-Jul-05	9-Aug-05	22-Aug-05	8-Sep-05	23-Sep-05	Grand Total	
	Arachnida		23	19	32	11	15	40	41	18	190	
	Blattaria		0	0	1	1	2	3	0	0	7	
	Coleoptera		14	22	18	33	16	12	4	3	122	
	Coleoptera larva		0	0	0	1	0	0	1	1	3	
	Collembola		0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	
	Diptera		53	39	71	47	23	29	2	0	264	
	Hemiptera		1	0	1	1	2	5	0	1	11	
	Homoptera		12	4	33	26	14	19	1	2	111	
	Hymenoptera		89	60	104	150	59	66	8	14	550	
	Isopoda		0	9	0	0	0	0	0	0	9	
	Lepidoptera		7	2	10	12	13	24	16	15	99	
	Mecoptera		0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	2	
	Neuroptera		0	1	0	0	0	0	0	4	6	
	Orthoptera		0	0	3	3	2	0	2	0	10	
	Thysanoptera		0	0	0	0	0	3	0	0	3	
Unknown		0	0	1	2	1	0	0	0	4		
Grand Total		0	199	147	277	288	147	201	75	58	1392	
Ram Pasture	Order	31-May-05	16-Jun-05	27-Jun-05	12-Jul-05	26-Jul-05	9-Aug-05	22-Aug-05	8-Sep-05	23-Sep-05	Grand Total	
	Arachnida		14	11	7	7	9	19	13	9	89	
	Coleoptera		69	71	28	16	7	16	4	2	213	
	Coleoptera larva		0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	
	Collembola		0	4	0	12	0	1	100	3	120	
	Diptera		83	92	38	26	77	31	109	15	471	
	Hemiptera		1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	3	
	Homoptera		9	38	13	4	7	14	2	1	88	
	Hymenoptera		45	30	25	20	2	15	1	2	140	
	Lepidoptera		4	14	5	19	2	8	7	0	59	
	Orthoptera		2	4	3	2	5	5	0	0	21	
	Thysanoptera		0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	
	Trichoptera		0	0	0	0	0	0	3	0	3	
	Grand Total		0	227	264	120	108	109	110	239	32	1209
	SMB	Order	31-May-05	16-Jun-05	27-Jun-05	11-Jul-05	26-Jul-05	9-Aug-05	22-Aug-05	8-Sep-05	23-Sep-05	Grand Total
		Arachnida		2	1	1	4	6	8	10	7	39
Coleoptera			36	118	8	6	1	4	6	8	187	
Collembola			0	1	0	5	16	50	0	0	72	
Diptera			6	3	11	21	10	26	17	3	97	
Hemiptera			0	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	2	
Homoptera			2	15	10	12	18	67	13	9	146	
Hymenoptera			57	36	20	8	3	9	7	2	142	
Isopoda			1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	
Lepidoptera			0	1	1	5	3	6	13	6	35	
Mantodea			0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	
Orthoptera			1	2	1	1	2	4	1	2	14	
Thysanoptera			0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	2	
Unknown			0	0	1	1	0	0	2	0	4	
Grand Total			0	104	178	56	63	59	176	69	37	742
SMC		Order	31-May-05	16-Jun-05	27-Jun-05	11-Jul-05	26-Jul-05	9-Aug-05	22-Aug-05	8-Sep-05	23-Sep-05	Grand Total
	Arachnida		15	9	16	8	19	24	75	32	223	
	Coleoptera		10	106	69	74	46	44	5	2	359	
	Coleoptera larva		15	0	0	5	1	0	0	0	21	
	Collembola		2	0	16	0	18	2	0	6	47	
	Diptera		17	17	48	30	75	18	38	5	232	
	Hemiptera		1	0	1	2	2	3	1	0	11	
	Homoptera		3	8	20	40	110	75	46	15	323	
	Hymenoptera		29	22	40	56	32	27	6	5	220	
	Isopoda		0	0	2	0	0	0	0	1	3	
	Lepidoptera		0	3	9	2	18	3	11	5	3	
	Mantodea		0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	
	Orthoptera		1	5	7	4	11	4	17	0	49	
	Psocoptera		0	0	0	0	0	0	4	0	4	
	Thysanoptera		2	0	1	7	3	0	0	0	13	
	Unknown		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Grand Total		94	171	229	227	335	201	184	70	50	1561	
Total per date		205	1404	1956	1722	1393	830	1076	657	285	9360	

Appendix II. Total number of Coleoptera collected per date in HB'03.

Family	Genus species	HB03									HB03 Total
		31-May-05	15-Jun-05	27-Jun-05	11-Jul-05	26-Jul-05	08-Aug-05	22-Aug-05	08-Sep-05	23-Sep-05	
ADERIDAE	Eionus	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Caenocara	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
ANOBIIDAE	Ernobius	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
	Xyletinus lugubris	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
ANTHRIBIDAE	Trigonorhinus rotundatus	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Atellabidae 1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Atellabidae 2	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
APELLABIDAE	Eugnamptatus	0	3	13	3	0	0	0	0	0	19
	Merhynchites bicolor	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Metachroma quercatum	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Temnocerus	3	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	5
BRENTIDAE	Apioninae 1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Apioninae 2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Rhopalaplion longirostre?	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
BRUCHIDAE	Bruchidae 1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Bruchidae 2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Agrilus 1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Agrilus aurichalceus	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
BUPRESTIDAE	Agrilus ruficollis	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Brachys ovatus	0	3	2	0	1	1	0	0	0	7
	Cantharis 1	0	8	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	12
CANTHARIDAE	Cantharis 2	0	7	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	7
	Ditemnus bidentatus	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Malthodes	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
CARABIDAE	Lebia viridis	0	0	1	5	3	0	0	0	0	9
	Altica	0	0	0	11	1	0	0	0	0	12
	Bassareus clathratus	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
	Calligrapha lunata	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Cryptocephalus calidus	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	2
	Cryptocephalus gibbicollis	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Cryptocephalus guttulatus	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Cryptocephalus n. notatus	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
	Cryptocephalus n. quadrimaculatus	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Neochlamisus	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	2	1	5
	Pachybrachis luridus	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Pachybrachis sp.	1	1	3	6	2	0	0	0	0	13
	Spintherophyta globosa	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Stenispis metallica	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Systema hudsonias	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Triachus atomus	1	10	32	12	4	0	0	0	0	59
	Triachus cerinus	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
CLERIDAE	Phyllobaenus affiliata	0	0	0	0	0	2	2	0	0	4
	Phyllobaenus h. difficilis	0	2	0	4	4	4	0	0	0	14
	Phyllobaenus humeralis	0	5	3	1	1	0	0	0	0	10
	Brachiacantha felina	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1
	Brachiacantha indubitabilis	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
COCCINELLIDAE	Cycloneda munda	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	3
	Harmonia axyridis	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Hyperaspis	1	2	4	3	0	5	3	1	1	20
	Mulsantina	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1
	Propylaea quadrimaculata	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Scymnus	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
CORYLOPHIDAE	Corylophidae	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Curculionidae 1	0	0	7	0	0	0	0	0	0	7
	Curculionidae 2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Curculionidae 3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Curculionidae 4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Curculionidae 5	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
CURCULIONIDAE	Curculionidae 6	4	0	2	0	0	1	0	0	0	7
	Curculionidae 7	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Curculionidae 8	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Curculionidae 9	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Curculionidae 10	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Curculionidae 11	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Curculionidae 12	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
ELATERIDAE	Ampedus	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Cardiophorus convexus	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Cardiophorus gagetes	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1
	Elatridae 1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Limonius basillaris	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	2
	Melanotus 1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Melanotus hylopsi	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Melanotus morosus	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
EUCNEMIDAE	Deltometopus amoenicornis	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
LAMPYRIDAE	Lucidota	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Photinus lucifera Melsh.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
LATRIDIIDAE	Corticaria	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	2
	Melanopthalma	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	1	3
LYCIDAE	Leptocleptes basalis	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
MELANDRYIDAE	Scotochroides antennatus	0	0	0	1	1	2	0	0	0	4
MELYRIDAE	Ablechus	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1
	Mordellid 1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Mordellid 2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
MORDELLIDAE	Mordellid 3	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	2
	Mordellistena	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Mordellochroa scapularis (Say)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
MYCETOPHAGIDAE	Litarus	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
NEMONYCHIDAE	Cimberis pilosus	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
NITIDULIDAE	Colopterus	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Meliogethes	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
PHALACRIDAE	Phalacrus politus	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Hoplia modesta	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
SCARABAEIDAE	Serica 1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Serica blatchleyi	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Serica iricolor	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
SCIRTIDAE	Cyphon variabilis	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1
SCYDMAENIDAE	Euconnus	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
STAPHYLINIDAE	Staphylinidae	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2
	Hymenorus	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
TENEBRIONIDAE	Isomira	0	1	13	1	0	0	0	0	0	15
	Paratenetus punctatus	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1
THROSCIDAE	Aulonothroscus	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Grand Total	15	48	92	50	20	15	7	4	3	254
	Species Richness	9	16	16	13	11	6	4	3	3	35

Appendix III. Total number of Coleoptera collected per date in HPG.

Family	Genus species	HPG								HPG Total
		16-Jun-05	27-Jun-05	12-Jul-05	26-Jul-05	9-Aug-05	22-Aug-05	8-Sep-05	23-Sep-05	
ADERIDAE	Elonus	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
ANOBIIDAE	Caenocara	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Ernobius	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Xyletinus lugubris	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
ANTHRIBIDAE	Trigonorhinus rotundatus	1	2	0	0	0	1	1	0	5
ATELLABIDAE	Atellabidae 1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Atellabidae 2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Eugnampatus	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1
	Merhyncites bicolor	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
	Metachroma quercatum	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Temnocerus	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	2
BRENTIDAE	Apioninae 1	4	2	2	0	1	0	0	0	9
	Apioninae 2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Rhopalapion longirostre?	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
BRUCHIDAE	Bruchidae 1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Bruchidae 2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
BUPRESTIDAE	Agrilus 1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Agrilus aurichalceus	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Agrilus ruficollis	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1
	Brachys ovatus	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	2
CANTHARIDAE	Cantharis 1	13	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	15
	Cantharis 2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Ditemnus bidentatus	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1
	Malthodes	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
CARABIDAE	Lebia viridis	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1
CHRYSOMELIDAE	Altica	0	12	136	1	0	2	0	0	151
	Bassareus clathratus	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Calligrapha lunata	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Cryptocephalus calidus	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
	Cryptocephalus gibbicollis	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Cryptocephalus guttulatus	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Cryptocephalus n. notatus	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Cryptocephalus n. quadrimaculatus	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Neochamsius	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1
	Pachybrachis luridus	3	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	6
	Pachybrachis sp.	0	7	0	1	0	0	0	0	8
	Spintherophyta globosa	11	8	0	0	0	0	0	1	20
	Stenispia metallica	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
	Systema hudsonias	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Triachus atomus	16	9	8	3	1	0	0	0	37
	Triachus cerinus	1	12	2	1	0	0	0	0	16
	CLERIDAE	Phyllobaenus affliata	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Phyllobaenus h. difficilis		0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1
Phyllobaenus humeralis		1	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	3
COCCINELLIDAE	Brachiachantha felina	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Brachiachantha indubitalis	0	2	0	2	0	0	0	0	4
	Cycloneda munda	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
	Harmonia axyridis	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
	Hyperaspis	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	2
	Mulsantina	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1
	Propylea quadrimaculata	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
Scymnus	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
CORYLOPHIDAE	Corylophidae	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
CURCULIONIDAE	Curculionidae 1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Curculionidae 2	0	3	0	1	1	0	0	0	5
	Curculionidae 3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Curculionidae 4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Curculionidae 5	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	2
	Curculionidae 6	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Curculionidae 7	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Curculionidae 8	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Curculionidae 9	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Curculionidae 10	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Curculionidae 11	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Curculionidae 12	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
ELATERIDAE	Ampedus	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Cardiophorus convexus	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1
	Cardiophorus gagetes	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Elateridae 1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Limonium basillaris	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Melanotus 1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
	Melanotus hyllopsi	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Melanotus morosus	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
EUCNEMIDAE	Deltometopus amoenicornis	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
LAMPYRIDAE	Lucidota	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Photinus lucifera Melsh.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
LATRIDIIDAE	Corticarina	0	0	0	1	2	0	0	0	3
	Melanophthalma	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
LYCIDAE	Leptocheilus basalis	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
MELANDRYIDAE	Scotochroides antennatus	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
MELYRIDAE	Ablechrus	0	0	1	1	0	1	0	0	3
MORDELLIDAE	Mordellid 1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Mordellid 2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Mordellid 3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Mordellistena	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Mordellochroa scapularis (Say)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
MYCETOPHAGIDAE	Litargus	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1
NEMONYCHIDAE	Cimberis pilosus	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
NITIDULIDAE	Colopterus	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Meligethes	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
PHALACRIDAE	Phalacrus politus	0	0	1	2	7	1	0	0	11
	Hoplia modesta	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2
SCARABAEIDAE	Serica 1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Serica blatchleyi	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2
	Serica iricolor	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
SCIRTIDAE	Cyphon variabilis	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
SCYDMAENIDAE	Euconnus	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
STAPHYLINIDAE	Staphylinidae	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
TENEBRIONIDAE	Hymenorus	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Isomira	1	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	4
	Paratenetus punctatus	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
THROSCIDAE	Aulonothroscus	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Grand Total	60	68	157	19	16	6	1	1	328
	Species Richness	16	17	13	15	8	5	1	1	39

Appendix IV. Total number of Coleoptera collected per date in MRM.

Family	Genus species	MRM						MRM Total
		16-Jun-05	27-Jun-05	11-Jul-05	26-Jul-05	22-Aug-05	8-Sep-05	
ADERIDAE	Elonus	0	0	0	4	0	0	4
ANOBIIDAE	Caenocara	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Ernobius	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
ANTHRIBIDAE	Xyletinus lugubris	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Trigonorhinus rotundatus	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
ATELLABIDAE	Atellabidae 1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Atellabidae 2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Eugnamptatus	1	7	6	2	0	0	16
	Merhyncites bicolor	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Metachroma quercatum	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
BRENTIDAE	Temnocerus	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Apioninae 1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Apioninae 2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
BRUCHIDAE	Rhopalapion longirostre?	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Bruchidae 1	1	0	0	0	0	0	1
BUPRESTIDAE	Bruchidae 2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Agrilus 1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Agrilus aurichalceus	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
CANTHARIDAE	Agrilus ruficollis	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Brachys ovatus	5	12	1	3	0	0	21
	Cantharis 1	1	0	0	0	0	0	1
	Cantharis 2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
CHRYSEMELIDAE	Ditemnus bidentatus	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Malthodes	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Lebia viridis	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Altica	0	0	0	1	1	0	2
	Bassareus clathratus	0	4	1	0	0	0	5
	Calligrapha lunata	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Cryptocephalus calidus	4	0	0	0	0	0	4
	Cryptocephalus gibbicollis	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Cryptocephalus guttulatus	0	1	4	0	0	0	5
	Cryptocephalus n. notatus	0	2	1	2	0	0	5
COCCINELLIDAE	Cryptocephalus n. quadrimaculatus	2	1	0	0	0	0	3
	Neochlamisus	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Pachybrachis luridus	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Pachybrachis sp.	1	2	17	10	1	0	31
	Spintherophyta globosa	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Stenispis metallica	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Systema hudsonias	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Triachus atomus	8	44	93	14	0	0	159
	Triachus cerinus	0	0	0	1	0	0	1
	CLERIDAE	Phyllobaenus affiliata	0	0	0	1	0	0
Phyllobaenus h. difficilis		0	5	2	0	0	0	7
Phyllobaenus humeralis		11	4	3	11	0	0	29
CORYLOPHIDAE	Brachiacantha felina	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Brachiacantha indubitalis	1	0	0	0	0	0	1
	Cycloneda munda	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Harmonia axyridis	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Hyperaspis	0	1	0	0	1	1	3
	Mulsantina	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Propylea quadrimaculata	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
CURCULIONIDAE	Scymnus	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Corylophidae	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Curculionidae 1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Curculionidae 2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Curculionidae 3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Curculionidae 4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Curculionidae 5	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Curculionidae 6	0	0	0	0	2	0	2
	Curculionidae 7	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Curculionidae 8	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Curculionidae 9	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Curculionidae 10	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
ELATERIDAE	Curculionidae 11	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Curculionidae 12	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Ampedus	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Cardiophorus convexus	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Cardiophorus gagetes	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Elateridae 1	0	1	0	0	0	0	1
	Limonium basillaris	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Melanotus 1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Melanotus hylipsi	2	1	0	1	0	0	4	
Melanotus morosus	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	
EUCNEMIDAE	Deltometopus amoenicornis	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
LAMPYRIDAE	Lucidata	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Photinus lucifera Melsh.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
LATRIDIIDAE	Corticarina	2	0	0	1	0	0	3
	Melanophthalma	0	0	0	1	0	0	1
LYCIDAE	Leptocoletes basalis	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
MELANDRYIDAE	Scotochroides antennatus	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
MELYRIDAE	Ablechrus	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
MORDELLIDAE	Mordellid 1	0	0	2	0	0	0	2
	Mordellid 2	0	0	2	0	0	0	2
	Mordellid 3	0	1	0	0	0	0	1
	Mordellistena	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Mordellochroa scapularis (Say)	0	2	0	0	0	0	2
MYCETOPHAGIDAE	Litargus	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
NEMONYCHIDAE	Cimberis pilosus	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
NITIDULIDAE	Colopterus	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Meligethes	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
PHALACRIDAE	Phalacrus politus	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
SCARABAEIDAE	Hoplia modesta	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Serica 1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Serica blatchleyi	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Serica iricolor	0	12	1	1	0	0	14
SCIRTIDAE	Cyphon variabilis	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
SCYDMAENIDAE	Euconnus	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
STAPHYLINIDAE	Staphylinidae	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Hymenorus	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
TENEBRIONIDAE	Isomira	0	0	0	3	0	0	3
	Paratenetus punctatus	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
THROSCIDAE	Aulonothroscus	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Grand Total	39	100	134	55	5	1	334
	Species Richness	12	16	13	14	4	1	31

Appendix V. Total number of Coleoptera collected per date in PPSO.

Family	Genus species	PPSO									PPSO Total
		16-Jun-05	27-Jun-05	11-Jul-05	26-Jul-05	9-Aug-05	22-Aug-05	8-Sep-05	23-Sep-05		
ADERIDAE	Elonus	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	2
ANOBIIDAE	Caenocara	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
	Ernobius	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Xyletinus lugubris	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
ANTHRIBIDAE	Trigonorhinus rotundatus	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
ATELLABIDAE	Atellabidae 1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
	Atellabidae 2	0	1	0	0	3	1	0	0	0	5
	Eugnamptatus	0	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	3
	Merrhyncites bicolor	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Metachroma quercatum	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Temnocerus	0	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	3
BRENTIDAE	Apioninae 1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Apioninae 2	0	0	1	3	2	0	0	0	0	6
	Rhopalapion longirostre?	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
BRUCHIDAE	Bruchidae 1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Bruchidae 2	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1
BUPRESTIDAE	Agrilus 1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Agrilus aurichalceus	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Agrilus ruficollis	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
CANTHARIDAE	Brachys ovatus	0	0	1	1	0	1	2	0	0	5
	Cantharis 1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Cantharis 2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
CARABIDAE	Ditemnus bidentatus	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Malthodes	0	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3
	Lebia viridis	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
CHRYSOMELIDAE	Altica	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Bassareus clathratus	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Calligrapha lunata	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Cryptocephalus calidus	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Cryptocephalus gibbicollis	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Cryptocephalus guttulatus	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Cryptocephalus n. notatus	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Cryptocephalus n. quadrimaculatus	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Neochlamisus	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Pachybrachis luridus	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Pachybrachis sp.	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	3
	Spintherophyta globosa	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
	Stenispa metallica	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Systema hudsonias	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Triachus atomus	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1
Triachus cerinus	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
CLERIDAE	Phyllobaenus affliata	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1
	Phyllobaenus h. difficilis	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Phyllobaenus humeralis	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1
COCCINELLIDAE	Brachiacantha felina	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Brachiacantha indubitatis	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Cycloneda munda	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Harmonia axyridis	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Hyperaspis	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Mulsantina	0	0	0	2	1	0	1	0	0	4
	Propylea quadrimaculata	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Scymnus	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
CORYLOPHIDAE	Corylophidae	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1
CURCULIONIDAE	Curculionidae 1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Curculionidae 2	0	0	0	0	0	3	0	0	0	3
	Curculionidae 3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Curculionidae 4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Curculionidae 5	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Curculionidae 6	5	2	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	8
	Curculionidae 7	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1
	Curculionidae 8	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
	Curculionidae 9	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2
	Curculionidae 10	1	2	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	4
	Curculionidae 11	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	2	0	3
	Curculionidae 12	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
ELATERIDAE	Ampedus	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Cardiophorus convexus	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Cardiophorus gagetes	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Elateridae 1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Limonium basillaris	0	3	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	5
	Melanotus 1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Melanotus hyllopsi	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
Melanotus morosus	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
EUCNEMIDAE	Deltometopus amoenicornis	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
LAMPYRIDAE	Lucidota	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
	Photinus lucifera Melsh.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
LATRIDIIDAE	Corticarina	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1
	Melanophthalma	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1
LYCIDAE	Leptocleptes basalis	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1
MELANDRYIDAE	Scotochroides antennatus	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	2
MELYRIDAE	Ablechrus	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
MORDELLIDAE	Mordellid 1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Mordellid 2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Mordellid 3	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1
	Mordellistena	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Mordellochroa scapularis (Say)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
MYCETOPHAGIDAE	Litargus	4	2	0	9	5	4	0	0	0	24
NEMONYCHIDAE	Cimberis pilosus	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
NITIDULIDAE	Colopterus	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1
	Meligethes	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
PHALACRIDAE	Phalacrus politus	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
SCARABAEIDAE	Hoplia modesta	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Serica 1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Serica blatchleyi	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Serica iricolor	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
SCIRTIDAE	Cyphon variabilis	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
SCYDMAENIDAE	Euconnus	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
STAPHYLINIDAE	Staphylinidae	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	2
TENEBRIONIDAE	Hymenorus	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Isomira	0	1	5	6	0	0	0	0	0	12
	Paratenetus punctatus	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
THROSCIDAE	Aulonothroscus	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	2
Grand Total		14	22	18	33	16	12	4	3		122
Species Richness		6	15	14	16	9	7	3	2		43

Appendix VI. Total number of Coleoptera collected per date in RP.

Family	Genus species	RP								RP Total
		16-Jun-05	27-Jun-05	12-Jul-05	26-Jul-05	09-Aug-05	22-Aug-05	08-Sep-05	23-Sep-05	
ADERIDAE	Elonus	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Caenocara	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
ANOBIIDAE	Ernobius	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Xyletinus lugubris	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	2
ANTHRIBIDAE	Trigonorhinus rotundatus	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Atellabidae 1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Atellabidae 2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
APELLABIDAE	Eugnamptatus	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Merhynchites bicolor	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Metachroma quercatum	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	2
	Temnocerus	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	2
	Apioninae 1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
BRENTIDAE	Apioninae 2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Rhopalapion longirostre?	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
BRUCHIDAE	Bruchidae 1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Bruchidae 2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Agrilus 1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
BUPRESTIDAE	Agrilus aurichalceus	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
	Agrilus ruficollis	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Brachys ovatus	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Cantharis 1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
	Cantharis 2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
CANTHARIDAE	Ditemnus bidentatus	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Malthodes	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
CARABIDAE	Lebia viridis	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	2
	Altica	1	4	0	0	0	13	0	1	19
	Bassareus clathratus	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Calligrapha lunata	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Cryptocephalus calidus	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Cryptocephalus gibbicollis	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
	Cryptocephalus guttulatus	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Cryptocephalus n. notatus	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Cryptocephalus n. quadrimaculatus	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
CHRYSOMELIDAE	Neochlamisus	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Pachybrachis luridus	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
	Pachybrachis sp.	14	12	2	4	0	1	0	0	33
	Spintherophyta globosa	0	0	0	0	0	0	4	0	4
	Stenispia metallica	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Systema hudsonias	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	2
	Triachus atomus	45	41	17	8	5	0	0	0	116
	Triachus cerinus	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Phyllobaenus affiliata	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
CLERIDAE	Phyllobaenus h. difficilis	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1
	Phyllobaenus humeralis	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Brachiacantha felina	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Brachiacantha indubitatis	0	6	1	0	0	0	0	0	7
	Cycloneda munda	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
COCCINELLIDAE	Harmonia axyridis	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Hyperaspis	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Mulsantina	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Propylea quadrimaculata	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Scymnus	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
CORYLOPHIDAE	Corylophidae	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Curculionidae 1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Curculionidae 2	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
	Curculionidae 3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Curculionidae 4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Curculionidae 5	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Curculionidae 6	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3
	Curculionidae 7	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Curculionidae 8	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Curculionidae 9	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Curculionidae 10	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Curculionidae 11	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Curculionidae 12	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Ampedus	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Cardiophorus convexus	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Cardiophorus gagetes	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
ELATERIDAE	Elaeteridae 1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Limonium basillaris	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Melanotus 1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Melanotus hyllopsi	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Melanotus morosus	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
EUCNEMIDAE	Deltometopus amoenicornis	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Lucidota	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
LAMPYRIDAE	Photinus lucifera Melsh.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Corticarina	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
LATRIDIIDAE	Melanoghalma	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
LYCIDAE	Leptocheilus basalis	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
MELANDRYIDAE	Scotochroides antennatus	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
MELYRIDAE	Ablechrus	0	0	3	2	1	0	0	0	6
	Mordellid 1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Mordellid 2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Mordellid 3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
MORDELLIDAE	Mordellistena	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Mordellochroa scapularis (Say)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
MYCETOPHAGIDAE	Litargus	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	2
NEMONYCHIDAE	Cimberis pilosus	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
NITIDULIDAE	Colopterus	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Meligethes	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
PHALACRIDAE	Phalacrus politus	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1
	Hoplia modesta	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
SCARABAEIDAE	Serica 1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
	Serica blatchleyi	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Serica iricolor	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
SCIRTIDAE	Cyphon variabilis	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
SCYDMAENIDAE	Euconus	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
STAPHYLINIDAE	Staphylinidae	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Hymenorus	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1
TENEBRIONIDAE	Isomira	0	3	1	0	0	0	0	0	4
	Paratenetus punctatus	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
THROSCIDAE	Aulonothroscus	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Grand Total	69	71	28	16	7	16	4	2	213
	Species Richness	10	10	8	5	3	4	1	2	23

Appendix VII. Total number of Coleoptera collected per date in SMB.

Family	Genus species	SMB							SMB Total	
		16-Jun-05	27-Jun-05	11-Jul-05	26-Jul-05	09-Aug-05	22-Aug-05	08-Sep-05		23-Sep-05
ADERIDAE	Eionus	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
ANOBIIDAE	Caenocara	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Ernobius	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
ANTHRIBIDAE	Xyletinus lugubris	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Trigonorhinus rotundatus	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
ATELLABIDAE	Atellabidae 1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Atellabidae 2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Eugnampatus	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Merhynchites bicolor	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
	Metachroma quercatum	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
BRENTIDAE	Temnocerus	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Apioninae 1	0	4	0	1	1	0	0	0	6
	Apioninae 2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Rhopalalopion longirostre?	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	2
BRUCHIDAE	Bruchidae 1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Bruchidae 2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
BUPRESTIDAE	Agrilus 1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Agrilus aurichalceus	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Agrilus ruficollis	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	2
	Brachys ovatus	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
CANTHARIDAE	Cantharis 1	15	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	17
	Cantharis 2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Ditemnus bidentatus	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Malthodes	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
CARABIDAE	Lebia viridis	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
CHRYSOMELIDAE	Altica	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1
	Bassareus clathratus	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1
	Calligrapha lunata	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Cryptocephalus calidus	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Cryptocephalus gibbicollis	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Cryptocephalus guttulatus	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Cryptocephalus n. notatus	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Cryptocephalus n. quadrimaculatus	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Neochlamisus	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Pachybrachis luridus	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Pachybrachis sp.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Spintherophyta globosa	4	1	0	0	0	1	3	7	16
	Stenispis metallica	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Systema hudsonias	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Triachus atomus	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
Triachus cerinus	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
CLERIDAE	Phyllobaenus affiliata	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Phyllobaenus h. difficilis	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
	Phyllobaenus humeralis	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1
COCCINELLIDAE	Brachiacantha felina	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Brachiacantha indubitatis	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
	Cycloneda munda	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Harmonia axyridis	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Hyperaspis	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Mulsantina	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Propylea quadrimaculata	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
	Scymnus	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1
CORYLOPHIDAE	Corylophidae	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
CURCULIONIDAE	Curculionidae 1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Curculionidae 2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Curculionidae 3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Curculionidae 4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Curculionidae 5	0	5	3	1	0	2	2	0	13
	Curculionidae 6	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Curculionidae 7	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Curculionidae 8	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Curculionidae 9	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Curculionidae 10	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Curculionidae 11	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Curculionidae 12	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
ELATERIDAE	Ampedus	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2
	Cardiophorus convexus	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
	Cardiophorus gagetes	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Elaterridae 1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Limonius basillaris	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Melanotus 1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Melanotus hylapsi	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Melanotus morosus	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
EUCNEMIDAE	Deltometopus amoenicornis	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
LAMPYRIDAE	Lucidota	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Photinus lucifera Melsh.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
LATRIDIIDAE	Corticaria	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
LYCIDAE	Melanopthalma	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1
	Leptocheilus basalus	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
MELANDRYIDAE	Scotochroides antennatus	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
MELYRIDAE	Ablechrus	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
MORDELLIDAE	Mordellid 1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Mordellid 2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Mordellid 3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Mordellistena	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1
	Mordellochroa scapularis (Say)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
MYCETOPHAGIDAE	Litargus	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
NEMONYCHIDAE	Cimberis pilosus	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
NITIDULIDAE	Colopterus	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Meligethes	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2
PHALACRIDAE	Phalacrus politus	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1
SCARABAEIDAE	Hoplia modesta	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Serica 1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Serica blatchleyi	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Serica iricolor	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
SCIRTIDAE	Cyphon variabilis	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
SCYDMAENIDAE	Euconus	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
STAPHYLINIDAE	Staphylinidae	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
TENEBRIONIDAE	Hymenurus	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Isomira	10	102	1	1	0	0	0	0	114
	Paratenetus punctatus	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
THROSCIDAE	Aulonothroscus	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Grand Total		36	118	8	6	1	4	6	8	187
Species Richness		8	9	6	5	1	3	3	2	22

Appendix VIII. Total number of Coleoptera collected per date in SMC.

Family	Genus species	SMC										SMC Total
		31-May-05	16-Jun-05	27-Jun-05	11-Jul-05	26-Jul-05	09-Aug-05	22-Aug-05	08-Sep-05	23-Sep-05		
ADERIDAE	Elonus	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
ANOBIIDAE	Caenocara	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Ernobius	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Xyletinus lugubris	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
ANTHRIBIDAE	Trigonorhinus rotundatus	1	1	3	1	21	16	2	0	1		46
ATELLABIDAE	Atellabidae 1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Atellabidae 2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Eugnamptatus	0	0	2	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	5
	Merhynchites bicolor	0	0	1	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	3
	Metachroma quercatum	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Temnocerus	0	0	1	7	0	0	0	0	0	0	8
BRENTIDAE	Apioninae 1	0	0	1	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	3
	Apioninae 2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Rhopalapion longirostre?	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
BRUCHIDAE	Bruchidae 1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Bruchidae 2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
BUPRESTIDAE	Agrilus 1	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2
	Agrilus aurichalceus	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2
	Agrilus ruficollis	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
	Brachys ovatus	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
CANTHARIDAE	Cantharis 1	0	91	27	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	120
	Cantharis 2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Ditemnus bidentatus	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	2
	Malthodes	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3
CARABIDAE	Lebia viridis	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	2
CHRYSOMELIDAE	Altica	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1
	Bassareus clathratus	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Calligrapha lunata	0	1	0	0	0	0	2	1	0	0	4
	Cryptocephalus calidus	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Cryptocephalus gibbicollis	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Cryptocephalus guttulus	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Cryptocephalus n. notatus	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
	Cryptocephalus n. quadrimaculatus	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Neochlamisus	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Pachybrachis luridus	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Pachybrachis sp.	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
	Spintherophyta globosa	3	5	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	12
	Stenispis metallica	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
	Systema hudsonias	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Triachus atomus	0	2	0	10	0	0	0	0	0	0	12
		Triachus cerinus	0	0	17	20	0	0	0	0	0	0
CLERIDAE	Phyllobaenus affilita	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Phyllobaenus h. difficilis	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
	Phyllobaenus humeralis	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
COCCINELLIDAE	Brachiacantha felina	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Brachiacantha indubitata	0	0	0	2	1	0	0	0	0	0	3
	Cycloneda munda	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Harmonia axyridis	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Hyperaspis	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
	Mulsantina	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Propylea quadrimaculata	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Scymnus	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
CORYLOPHIDAE	Corylophidae	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
CURCULIONIDAE	Curculionidae 1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Curculionidae 2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Curculionidae 3	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1
	Curculionidae 4	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
	Curculionidae 5	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Curculionidae 6	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Curculionidae 7	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Curculionidae 8	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Curculionidae 9	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1
	Curculionidae 10	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Curculionidae 11	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
		Curculionidae 12	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
ELATERIDAE	Ampedus	2	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3
	Cardiophorus convexus	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Cardiophorus gagates	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Elateridae 1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Limonium basilaris	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Melanotus 1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Melanotus hylolopi	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Melanotus morosus	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
EUCNEMIDAE	Deltometopus amoenicornis	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
LAMPYRIDAE	Lucidota	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Photinus lucifera Melsh.	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	2
LATRIDIIDAE	Corticarina	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Melanopthalma	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1
LYCIDAE	Leptoceletes basalus	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
MELANDRYIDAE	Scotochroides antennatus	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
MELYRIDAE	Ablechrus	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
MORDELLIDAE	Mordellid 1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Mordellid 2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Mordellid 3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Mordellistena	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Mordellochroa scapularis (Say)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
MYCETOPHAGIDAE	Litargus	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
NEMONYCHIDAE	Cimberis pilosus	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
NITIDULIDAE	Colopterus	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Meligethes	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
PHALACRIDAE	Phalacrus politus	0	0	0	0	13	27	1	0	0	0	41
SCARABAEIDAE	Hoplia modesta	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Serica 1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Serica blatchleyi	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Serica iricolor	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
SCIRTIDAE	Cyphon variabilis	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
SCYDMAENIDAE	Euconus	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
STAPHYLINIDAE	Staphylinidae	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
TENEBRIONIDAE	Hymenorus	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Isomira	0	0	7	27	1	0	0	0	0	0	35
	Paratenetus punctatus	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
THROSCIDAE	Aulonothroscus	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Grand Total	10	106	69	74	46	44	5	2	3		359
	Species Richness	6	11	15	11	12	3	3	2	2		37

Appendix IX. Summary of Coleoptera species collected per site in sweep samples during 2005.

Family	Taxon	HB03	HPG	MRM	PPSO	RP	SMB	SMC	Grand Total	% Total
ADERIDAE	Elonus sp.?	0	0	4	2	0	0	0	6	0.34%
ANOBIIDAE	Caenocara sp.	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0.06%
	Ernobius sp.	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0.06%
	Xyletinus lugubris	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	2	0.11%
ANTHRIBIDAE	Trigonorhinus rotundatus	0	5	0	0	0	0	46	51	2.85%
ATELLABIDAE	Atellabidae 1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0.06%
	Atellabidae 2	1	0	0	5	0	0	0	6	0.34%
	Eugnampatus	19	1	16	3	0	0	5	44	2.46%
	Merhynchites bicolor	0	1	0	0	0	1	3	5	0.28%
	Metachroma quercatum	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	2	0.11%
Temnocerus	5	2	0	3	2	0	8	20	1.12%	
BRENTIDAE	Apioninae 1	0	9	0	0	0	6	3	18	1.01%
	Apioninae 2	0	0	0	6	0	0	0	6	0.34%
	Rhopalapion longirostre	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	2	0.11%
BRUCHIDAE	Bruchidae 1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	0.06%
	Bruchidae 2	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0.06%
BUPRESTIDAE	Agrilus 1	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	2	0.11%
	Agrilus aurichalceus	0	0	0	0	1	0	2	3	0.17%
	Agrilus ruficollis	0	1	0	0	0	2	1	4	0.22%
	Brachys ovatus	7	2	21	5	0	0	0	35	1.95%
CANTHARIDAE	Cantharis 1	12	15	1	0	1	17	12	166	9.27%
	Cantharis 2	7	0	0	0	0	0	0	7	0.39%
	Ditemnus bidentatus	0	1	0	0	0	0	2	3	0.17%
	Malthodes	0	0	0	3	0	0	3	6	0.34%
CARABIDAE	Lebia viridis	9	1	0	0	2	0	2	14	0.78%
CHRYSOMELIDAE	Altica	12	151	2	0	19	1	1	186	10.39%
	Bassareus clathratus	1	0	5	0	0	1	0	7	0.39%
	Calligrapha lunata	0	0	0	0	0	0	4	4	0.22%
	Cryptocephalus calidus	2	1	4	0	0	0	0	7	0.39%
	Cryptocephalus gibbicollis	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0.06%
	Cryptocephalus guttulatus	0	0	5	0	0	0	0	5	0.28%
	Cryptocephalus n. notatus	1	0	5	0	0	0	1	7	0.39%
	Cryptocephalus n. quadrimaculatus	0	0	3	0	0	0	0	3	0.17%
	Neochlamisus	5	1	0	0	0	0	0	6	0.34%
	Pachybrachis luridus	0	6	0	0	1	0	0	7	0.39%
	Pachybrachis sp.	13	8	31	3	33	0	1	89	4.97%
	Spintherophyta globosa	0	2	0	1	4	16	12	53	2.96%
	Steniska metallica	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	2	0.11%
	Systema hudsonias	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	2	0.11%
	Triachus atomus	59	37	159	1	116	1	12	385	21.50%
	Triachus cerinus	0	16	0	0	0	0	37	53	2.96%
CLERIDAE	Phyllobaenus affiliata	4	0	1	1	0	0	0	6	0.34%
	Phyllobaenus h. difficilis	14	1	7	0	1	1	1	25	1.40%
	Phyllobaenus humeralis	1	3	29	1	0	1	1	45	2.51%
COCCINELLIDAE	Brachiacantha felina	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0.06%
	Brachiacantha indubitatis	0	4	1	0	7	1	3	16	0.89%
	Cycloneda munda	3	1	0	0	0	0	0	4	0.22%
	Harmonia axyridis	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0.06%
	Hyperaspis	2	2	3	0	0	0	1	26	1.45%
	Mulsantina	1	1	0	4	0	0	0	6	0.34%
	Propylea quadrimaculata	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	2	0.11%
	Scymnus	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0.06%
CURCULIONIDAE	Corylophidae	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0.06%
	Curculionidae 1	7	0	0	0	0	0	0	7	0.39%
	Curculionidae 2	0	5	0	3	1	0	0	9	0.50%
	Curculionidae 3	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0.06%
	Curculionidae 4	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0.06%
	Curculionidae 5	0	2	0	0	0	13	0	15	0.84%
	Curculionidae 6	7	0	2	8	3	0	0	20	1.12%
	Curculionidae 7	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	0.06%
	Curculionidae 8	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0.06%
	Curculionidae 9	0	0	0	2	0	0	1	3	0.17%
	Curculionidae 10	0	0	0	4	0	0	0	4	0.22%
	Curculionidae 11	0	0	0	3	0	0	0	3	0.17%
	Curculionidae 12	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0.06%
ELATERIDAE	Ampedus	0	0	0	0	0	2	3	5	0.28%
	Cardiophorus convexus	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	2	0.11%
	Cardiophorus gagetes	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0.06%
	Elateridae 1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	0.06%
	Limonium basilaris	2	0	0	5	0	0	0	7	0.39%
	Melanotus 1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0.06%
	Melanotus hyllopsi	0	0	4	1	0	0	0	5	0.28%
Melanotus morosus	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	0.06%	
EUCNEMIDAE	Deltometopus amoenicornis	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0.06%
LAMPYRIDAE	Lucidota	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0.06%
	Photinus lucifera Melsh.	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	2	0.11%
LATRIDIIDAE	Corticarina	2	3	3	1	0	0	0	9	0.50%
	Melanopthalma	3	0	1	1	0	1	1	7	0.39%
LYCIDAE	Leptoceletes basalis	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0.06%
MELANDRYIDAE	Scotochroides antennatus	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	2	0.11%
MELYRIDAE	Ablechrus	4	3	0	1	6	0	0	14	0.78%
MORDELLIDAE	Mordellid 1	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	2	0.11%
	Mordellid 2	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	2	0.11%
	Mordellid 3	2	0	1	1	0	0	0	4	0.22%
	Mordellistena	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0.06%
	Mordellochroa scapularis (Say)	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	2	0.11%
MYCETOPHAGIDAE	Litarqus	0	1	0	24	2	0	1	28	1.56%
NEMONYCHIDAE	Cimberis pilosus	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0.06%
NITIDULIDAE	Colopterus	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0.06%
	Meligethes	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	2	0.11%
PHALACRIDAE	Phalacrus politus	0	11	0	0	1	1	41	54	3.02%
SCARABAEIDAE	Hoplia modesta	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	2	0.11%
	Serica 1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0.06%
	Serica blatchleyi	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	2	0.11%
	Serica iricolor	0	0	14	0	0	0	0	14	0.78%
SCIRTIDAE	Cyphon variabilis	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0.06%
SCYDMAENIDAE	Euconnus	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0.06%
STAPHYLINIDAE	Staphylinid 1	2	0	0	2	0	0	0	4	0.22%
TENEBRIONIDAE	Hymenorus	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0.06%
	Isomira	15	4	3	12	4	114	35	187	10.44%
	Paratenetus punctatus	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0.06%
THROSCIDAE	Aulonothroscus	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	2	0.11%
Grand Total		254	328	334	122	213	187	359	1797	
Family Richness		16	17	14	27	14	14	16	32	
Species Richness		34	38	30	40	23	22	34	101	

Appendix X. Summary of Coleoptera collected per date in sweep net samples during 2005.

Family	Taxon	31-May	15/16 June	27-Jun	11/12 July	26-Jul	8/9 August	22-Aug	8-Sep	23-Sep	Grand Total	% Total
ADERIDAE	Elonus	0	0	1	1	4	0	0	0	0	6	0.33%
	Caenocara	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0.06%
ANOBIIDAE	Ernobius	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0.06%
	Xyletinus lugubris	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0.11%
ANTHREBIDAE	Trigonorhinus rotundatus	1	2	5	1	21	16	3	1	1	51	2.84%
	Atellabidae 1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0.06%
	Atellabidae 2	1	0	1	0	0	3	1	0	0	6	0.33%
ATELLABIDAE	Eugnamptatus	0	4	23	14	3	0	0	0	0	44	2.45%
	Merhynchites bicolor	0	1	2	0	2	0	0	0	0	5	0.28%
	Metachroma quercatum	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	2	0.11%
	Temnocerus	3	1	5	1	1	0	0	0	0	20	1.11%
BRENTIDAE	Apioninae 1	0	4	7	2	2	3	0	0	0	18	1.00%
	Apioninae 2	0	0	0	1	3	2	0	0	0	6	0.33%
	Rhopalapion longirostre?	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	2	0.11%
BRUCHIDAE	Bruchidae 1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0.06%
	Bruchidae 2	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	0.06%
BUPRESTIDAE	Agrilus 1	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0.11%
	Agrilus aurichalceus	0	0	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	0.17%
	Agrilus ruficollis	0	1	0	1	2	0	0	0	0	4	0.22%
	Brachys ovatus	0	9	14	3	5	1	1	2	0	35	1.95%
CANTHARIDAE	Cantharis 1	0	39	35	2	0	0	0	0	0	166	9.24%
	Cantharis 2	0	7	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	7	0.39%
	Ditemnus bidentatus	0	0	0	0	3	0	0	0	0	3	0.17%
	Malthodes	3	0	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	6	0.33%
CARABIDAE	Lebia viridis	0	1	2	6	5	0	0	0	0	14	0.78%
	Altica	0	1	16	148	4	0	16	0	1	186	10.35%
	Bassareus clathratus	0	0	5	2	0	0	0	0	0	7	0.39%
	Calligrapha lunata	0	1	0	0	0	0	2	1	0	4	0.22%
	Cryptocephalus calidus	0	6	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	7	0.39%
	Cryptocephalus gibbicollis	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0.06%
	Cryptocephalus guttulatus	0	0	1	4	0	0	0	0	0	5	0.28%
	Cryptocephalus n. notatus	0	2	2	1	2	0	0	0	0	7	0.39%
	Cryptocephalus n. quadrimaculatus	0	2	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	0.17%
	Neochlamisus	1	1	0	0	0	0	1	2	1	6	0.33%
	Pachybrachis luridus	0	4	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	7	0.39%
	Pachybrachis sp.	1	16	25	26	18	1	2	0	0	89	4.95%
	Spintherophyta globosa	3	2	12	0	0	0	1	7	1	53	2.95%
	Stenispis metallica	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0.11%
	Systema hudsonias	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	2	0.11%
	Triachus atomus (Suffrain)	1	82	126	14	29	7	0	0	0	385	21.42%
	Triachus cerinus	0	1	29	22	1	0	0	0	0	53	2.95%
CLERIDAE	Phyllobaenus affiliata	0	0	0	0	1	2	3	0	0	6	0.33%
	Phyllobaenus h. diffractilis	0	2	7	6	6	4	0	0	0	25	1.39%
	Phyllobaenus humeralis	0	17	7	6	15	0	0	0	0	45	2.50%
COCCINELLIDAE	Brachiacantha felina	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	0.06%
	Brachiacantha indubitabilis	0	1	9	3	3	0	0	0	0	16	0.89%
	Cycloneda munda	1	1	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	4	0.22%
	Harmonia axyridis	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0.06%
	Hyperaspis	1	3	5	3	0	7	4	2	1	26	1.45%
	Mulsantina	0	0	0	0	3	2	0	1	0	6	0.33%
	Propylea quadrimaculata	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0.11%
	Scymnus	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0.06%
CORYLOPHIDAE	Corylophid 1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0.06%
CURCULIONIDAE	Curculionidae 1	0	0	7	0	0	0	0	0	0	7	0.39%
	Curculionidae 2	0	0	4	0	1	1	3	0	0	9	0.50%
	Curculionidae 3	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	0.06%
	Curculionidae 4	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0.06%
	Curculionidae 5	0	0	6	4	1	0	2	2	0	15	0.83%
	Curculionidae 6	4	8	4	1	0	1	2	0	0	20	1.11%
	Curculionidae 7	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	0.06%
	Curculionidae 8	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0.06%
	Curculionidae 9	0	2	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	3	0.17%
	Curculionidae 10	0	1	2	0	0	1	0	0	0	4	0.22%
	Curculionidae 11	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	2	3	0.17%
	Curculionidae 12	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0.06%
ELATERIDAE	Ampedus	2	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	5	0.28%
	Cardiophorus convexus	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	2	0.11%
	Cardiophorus gagetes	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0.06%
	Elatridae 1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0.06%
	Limonium basillaris	0	0	5	0	2	0	0	0	0	7	0.39%
	Melanotus 1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0.06%
	Melanotus hypopsi	0	2	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	5	0.28%
	Melanotus morosus	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0.06%
EUCNEMIDAE	Deltometopus amoenicornis	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0.06%
	Lucidota	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0.06%
LAMPYRIDAE	Photinus lucifera Melsheimer	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	2	0.11%
LATRIDIIDAE	Corticarina	0	2	2	0	2	3	0	0	0	9	0.50%
	Melanophthalma	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	2	2	7	0.39%
LYCIDAE	Leptocleptes basalis	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	0.06%
MELANDRYIDAE	Scotochroides antennatus	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	2	0.11%
MELYRIDAE	Ablechrus	0	0	0	6	4	3	1	0	0	14	0.78%
MORDELLIDAE	Mordellid 1	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	2	0.11%
	Mordellid 2	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	2	0.11%
	Mordellid 3	0	1	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	4	0.22%
	Mordellistena sp.	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0.06%
	Mordellochroa scapularis (Say)	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0.11%
MYCETOPHAGIDAE	Litargus	0	6	2	0	9	6	5	0	0	28	1.56%
NEMONYCHIDAE	Cimberis pilosus	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0.06%
NITIDULIDAE	Colopterus	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	0.06%
	Meligethes	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0.11%
PHALACRIDAE	Phalacrus politus	0	0	0	1	15	35	3	0	0	54	3.01%
SCARABAEIDAE	Hoplia modesta	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0.11%
	Serica 1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0.06%
	Serica blatchleyi	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0.11%
	Serica iricolor	0	0	12	1	1	0	0	0	0	14	0.78%
SCIRTIDAE	Cyphon variabilis	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0.06%
SCYDMAENIDAE	Euconnus	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0.06%
STAPHYLINIDAE	Staphylinidae	2	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	4	0.22%
	Hymenorus	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	0.06%
TENEBRIONIDAE	Isomira	0	12	129	35	11	0	0	0	0	187	10.41%
	Paratenetus punctatus	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0.06%
THROSCIDAE	Aulonothroscus	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	2	0.11%
	Grand Total	25	372	540	469	195	99	55	22	20	1797	
	Family Richness	8	21	21	20	24	13	13	8	6	32	
	Species Richness	15	50	55	44	47	20	21	11	9	101	